

THE ROLE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Annotation: This article highlights the understanding of the role of English in the world, the need to know its history, and the growing demand for this language in the modern world.

Key words: English language, learning techniques, students, invaluable world, firms need translators.

Аннотация: В этой статье освещается понимание роли английского языка в мире, необходимость знать его историю и растущий спрос на этот язык в современном мире.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, методы обучения, студенты, бесценный мир, фирмам нужны переводчики.

The role of the English language in the modern world is invaluable. English is believed to be the most commonly used language. More than 450 million people consider it to be native. Another 600-650 million citizens use English as an additional language for communication. It is in demand in many countries of the world. Knowledge of this language is also essential in order to study abroad. Those wishing to find a prestigious and well-paid job can't do without it.

To understand the role of the English language in the modern world, first of all, it is necessary to know its history. It's no secret that finding out exactly how a language was formed is almost impossible. It is known that the German invaders arrived and settled in Britain in the 5th century AD. They spoke Germanic. Specialists have a small amount of information about this period. This is due to the fact that no written archives and documents of the time were found. The formation of dialects is confirmed by sources from the 7th – 9th centuries. They all relate to the language that Alfred the Great called English in the 9th century.

It is believed that the speech of the Scandinavians is also quite strongly influenced the development of the English language.

For several centuries after the Norman Conquest, significant changes occurred in the English language. The inflectional system formed during that period is used today. According to it, grammar-specific generic endings are almost not used in English. Changes touched the vocabulary. There were borrowings from other languages, which eventually began to appear in writing.

In the Late Middle Ages and the modern period, stable processes of standardization of the English language took place. Written and colloquial speech continued to change. The so-called great movement of the vowels took place. From the beginning of the seventeenth

century, the influence of the English language was felt throughout the world. Over time, it began to be used by people from different countries.

The importance of the English language in the modern world today is quite large. Most recently, it was a foreign language for us, and today it is an international one. Therefore, now in all countries of the world English betrays great importance. Today children begin to study it at a preschool age.

Travelling to English speaking countries is only possible if you know and understand a foreign language. Actually almost every person wants to go on vacation abroad. Thanks to the knowledge of English, you can easily communicate with people not only in English-speaking countries. English is also well spoken by people whose work is related to tourists. If you know a foreign language, you can always easily ask for help in a foreign country. That is why you will feel confident abroad.

The role of the English language is evident to students who wish to get a decent education. Its knowledge allows you to study at any university.

Almost in any large library there are books in English. Detectives, novels, poems and other works can be read in the original, using a foreign language. No less valuable are the originals of technical literature. Thanks to English, you can more thoroughly explore the equipment or equipment of interest.

The relevance of learning English can also be explained by the rapid development of technology. Every year, experts from around the world create new inventions. They are given names that are most often English-speaking.

English plays an important role in the life of adolescents and young people. Computer games in English are very popular among gamers. Obviously many young people spend a considerable amount of free time using them. As a rule, at first new foreign games do not have Russian translation, so knowledge of a foreign language can help the gamer.

A large number of English words are present in the youth speech. Experts believe that this is due to the stereotypes and ideals that were created in adolescent society. Young people are confident that the standard of living in America is much higher than ours. Using English borrowing in their speech, they are in a certain way approaching their own kind of ideal.

Many students underestimate its importance. Most often, experts with knowledge of foreign are needed in the field of education and science. The highest level of proficiency in English must have students who wish to link their lives with information technology.

Undoubtedly English plays an important role in getting a job. People who want to get a prestigious and well-paid position must necessarily know English well. Those who speak English fluently can work for large companies as it is necessary to contact international partners. Most of employers pay more to employees who speak English. According to the research, candidates with knowledge of foreign earn about 10-40% more than their colleagues. It is worth noting that in some companies only those employees who are fluent in English are hired. Some firms need translators, that's why they are willing to train promising candidates at their own expense.

Students with knowledge of the English language have a huge advantage. Some firms, including large ones, are ready to hire inexperienced specialists and provide them with high wages if they own a foreign one.

The English language is the most important communicative tool at the international level. Modern man can not use the latest benefits of civilization without certain linguistic

knowledge. All spheres of our vital activity to some extent require knowledge of the English language.

Learning English is becoming more and more sought after. Any modern person should own it at least at the basic level.

English plays an important role in our lives. Its knowledge is necessary for people of all ages. English is associated with all spheres of life. Those who is going to get a prestigious education or job cannot do without it. Employees speaking English earn more than those who do not know it. This fact can serve as an excellent incentive to learn English vocabulary and grammar at any age.

References:

1. Словарь иностранных слов / Под ред. В.В.Бурцева, Н.М. Семенова.- М., 2005.
2. Энтони Гидденс Ускользящий мир. Как глобализация меняет нашу жизнь. – М.: «Весь Мир», 2004.
- 3.<https://infourok.ru/doklad-na-temu-rol-angliyskogo-yazika-v-sovremennom-mire-1703665.html>
4. <https://guruenglish.ru/dlya-chego-nuzhen-anglijskij-yazyk/>
5. <https://scienceforum.ru/2019/article/2018012260> .